

ROLE OF EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION IN BRIDGING INDUSTRY ACADEMIA GAP FOR STUDENT CAREER SHAPE

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Abstract:

Youth of today are considered as the wealth of nation and hence the future of nation depends widely on the appropriate employability of the youth. In the present scenario it is believed that “India’s destiny is being shaped both in four walls and outside the walls”, which means there is always a need for collaboration of non-formal education in the formal education structure to increase the youth potential in getting the jobs.

India is a developing country with ample of human resources available. With the growing economy, India is also witnessing the growth of education sector. However, Indian industry is not so convinced about the job – readiness of the graduates. There is an urgent need that Industries and Academia come together.

Key words: Academia, Formal education, Non – formal education

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Introduction:

Academia and practice Industry are just like seed and tree, a single seed has all components and is completely integrated and aligned with complete tree so in order to bridge the gap between academia and industry we need to create the seeds in the academia in the universities and colleges so that they become fruitful trees when they go to the industry. We also really need to understand what kind of fruit and seed is required in the industry.

People who are unemployed they are always complaining that there are very less jobs or no jobs in the market and on the other hand companies are complaining that there is no talent in the market .

Now a day’s companies have started training their own employees which is an alarming thing for the universities, educational institutions must realize that now companies are not accepting their graduates; there is something wrong in their graduates as they are not teaching them proper things. The university system means that you have to train a person for the corporate sector. If a student does not possess skill of MS Office, MS Excel, MS access , Email writing , interview techniques and creative thinking then what’s the point in sending them to the university ,actually they should learn all these things from their first semester. So in the current scenario it is the responsibility of all the educational institutions to impart practical skills to the students in the universities such as handling software, problem solving, case studies and ability to sell etc.

Objective

Objectives of writing this paper are as follows

- To find the expectations of the industry in the current scenario.

- To find the loop holes in the curriculum of the educational institutions.
- To find the solutions to bridge the gap between the educational institutions and the industries.

Why there is a gap?

There is a gap because they both have different Mindset, therefore both are living in two different worlds and have different goals entirely

Industry	Academic
Starving to survive	Starving for recognition from their peers
Short range goals	Long range goals
Prefers proven solution with a low risk	Interested in creating new solutions with a high innovation rate
Mainly concerned with costs	Mainly interested in the benefits

Academics is too theoretical and Industry is too practical.

Problems faced

After passing out from college students are very enthusiastic, very keen to do their work, creative, full of new ideas, having big dreams and plans but face a lot of problems in workplace because the knowledge which was imparted in college was not in depth.

Following are the problems which are faced by freshers in real world:-

- Ignorant of latest technology in the market
- No knowledge of do's and don'ts of any process
- No idea about what constitute good and bad quality work
- Technology is studied in college but its practical implementation is not known

Solution

The increased demand for training of graduates reveals a mismatch between academic education and industry requirements. This paper identifies the gap between academia and industry and presents solution to bridge it.

Learning a Foreign Language

The world is becoming global so, nowadays there is always a demand for people who can help bridge the communication gap between two or more Multi National Companies and their clients as well as in private and public sector.

Presently two languages are in demand First European language and secondly Asian. Under European language comes German, Spanish and French. Under Asian language come Japanese, Korean and Chinese. They are in demand because most of the businesses are done with these two countries. In this field three years degree course/ Diploma Courses / Advance Certification Course can be done from various universities like IGNOU, DU etc.

Opportunity and resources to learn a foreign language are much more easily available today than in the past, even you can also learn foreign languages through courses which are available online which make the process of learning to speak another language easily accessible to everyone and flexible too to fit into busy schedule.

If you are fluent in two or more languages it will give you an edge over monolingual candidates in job interviews. These opportunities exist in all types of companies like MNC, private and public and even in departments which range

from marketing to tourism. It is not at all surprising that lot of corporations requires candidates who are bilingual or multilingual.

Alignment of curriculum with industry needs is an imperative:

Due to changes in technological environment i.e introduction of Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine learning (ML) etc it has become very important for both industries and students to have knowledge of these technologies.

As per the dynamic nature of industry, it has become very important to frame the academic curriculums per industry expectation. Despite changes in almost every field, college curriculum is often rigid and hard to revise so; it is advisable that curriculum should be revised regularly with the changing industrial needs. For commerce students Tally, Excel should be made compulsory subjects in the curriculum.

Stress on skill-based education:

It has been observed that the core skills which are required by the corporate are changing at a greater pace and new skills like creative thinking, higher level problem solving, interpersonal skills, innovation; decision making will be in great demand in near future.

Skill-based education is lacking in all the higher education fields. The focus of management institutes should shift from traditional to skill based education with a more practical and dynamic approach. Therefore, besides imparting the core knowledge, academia should also try to focus on the soft skill development and behavioral aspects such as interpersonal skills, leadership capability, attitude, communication skills, and team spirit.

Workplace exposure through internships, live projects, and corporate interactions in B - Schools

Fresher do not have pre requisite experience so it become very important for B – schools to provide internships, Experience of handling live projects so that they will be able to know the actual working of corporate.

Internships or part-time projects provides practical insights about how the industry operates and expose students to the current realities of the workplace and it will also equip the students to adjust to the changing needs of the business once they actually join the industry. Such opportunities increase students' confidence as they learn a lot by being present in the workplace.

Faculties need to Reskill and Upskill themselves

Apart from only focusing on the curriculum structure, it is also important to provide the right exposure and training to the faculty also. Most of the faculties do not possess industry experience as a result of which teachers failed to imparting practical knowledge about industries to students. It will be great if the faculty can regularly undertake small – small industrial projects in collaboration with industry experts. This will help ensure that the faculty is in line with the current industrial trends.

Build student motivation:

Be it any skill, motivating student's plays a very important role. Every person is unique and their strengths lie in different area. Graduates should be given opportunities where they discover their strengths. It can be done by making students work on something out-of-the-box and providing them with strong encouragement. The out-of-the-box activity can be anything – organizing college fests, model making competition ,participating in case study competition, making them work with NGOs, providing opportunity to explore their creative side with activities like painting etc. all these activities help to identify what an individual is really good at. Students can be motivated by delegating more responsibilities to them and this will also increase their confidence

Build a balanced syllabus:

These days college syllabus is one of the highly debated topics. As per industrialist syllabus should be reshaped with latest topics. Syllabus should consist of 70% practical and 30% should be theoretical. E-learning should also be taken into consideration. Students should be given hands-on experience, assignments and projects. This will help them to increase their confidence and make them ready to step into their new career. Practical should be included in courses like BMS, BAF, BBI and BBA in subjects like Organisational behavior, marketing Management, communication etc. Some universities have already taken step in this direction

Provide workplace exposure:

When studying in colleges or universities, students are not aware about workplace expectations so, they should be given actual on sight training or hands – on experience .Hence students must be made aware by exposing them with real-time workplace experience.

Internships help to bridge the gap between academia and industry, some of the universities in India has already made it mandatory as a part of college curriculum. Internship is a open class room kind of a concept where there are no walls, no exams , no pre entrance exams the only pre – requisite to do all this is to have a passion to do excellent work .During their internship, graduates not only learn in terms of their job expectations but also learn about organisational behavioral aspects.

In addition to the internship students can be made aware about the corporate world by having different engagement programs with the industry. Some of them include having guest lecturers or webinars or workshop or seminars by different corporate experts on topics like Job-readiness, campus to corporate transition etc.

Findings

- In order to bridge the gap between industry and academia it is very important for the educational institutions to understand the need of industries and accordingly plan its curriculum.
- For example nowadays CA firms requires those students who have knowledge of tally, excel and financial accounting concepts.
- Companies also requires students for marketing for this communication skill, convincing power is required. Colleges should take effort in this direction.
- Students should be encouraged to do research work.
- Knowledge which is provided in colleges are not sufficient to be implemented in the practice.
- School learning is not applicable in the workplace.
- Lack of in-depth knowledge.
- To pass exams different skill sets are required and in workplace different skill sets are required
- Students should be mentally prepared to relearn the technology, process and working at the workplace from different perspective.
- Hands – on experience should be given to students.

Suggestions

- In the Board of Studies one or two members should be company CEO so that the syllabus can be prepared in accordance with the requirement of industry.
- Syllabus should be designed in such a way that it teaches new age skills.

ERJ**Conclusion**

From this paper we conclude that on an urgent basis it is very important to bridge industry-academia gap in order to increase employment opportunity and for this students, universities, organizations, colleges and government need to work in the same direction to make it happen and also lot of amendments are required in the University curriculum. Case study, on site project, problem solving should be added in syllabus.

In depth and detailed knowledge should be given to students by sending to industrial visits, educational trips, training, internship etc. Colleges should also organize seminars, webinars on job - readiness and guest lecturers to give insight of corporate working.

Bibliography

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